

METHODS OF INTRODUCING FICTION TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. The purpose of this work is to analyze the role and importance of fiction in the education of preschool children, their aesthetic upbringing, as well as the specific features and forms of children's literature in the development of speech in preschool children.

Keywords: artistic image, fiction, folklore, prose, illustration, moral-epic, moralaesthetic .

INTRODUCTION

Before school education age children with at work artistic word big place holds _ Children people fairy tales , poems , stories to hear good they see Children literature , first of all his own interesting content , artistic of images the beauty of the language expressiveness , poetic of words musicality with to the children joy give is enough The same at that time to the children educational effect shows . Great Russian democratic VG Belinsky children book education for It is written , " Education is great. " work , it is human fate solution he said _ was _ Artistic of literature expensive each of the child in terms of to growth effect it shows . Artistic literature to the child sweetheart country nature of people work and their lives _ doing works and showing heroism , children from his life received events , children games , pastimes and doing their work protection by doing gives _ Of people internal the world illuminate their _ characters , feelings , behavior are also described _ to events of the writer attitude showing artistic _ literature works the child to excitement , work to the heroes to pity or them to condemn forced does _

Most good artistic literature works in children something to something good-bad , fair-unfair , right-wrong , to themselves special one help gives _ Children of the book interesting content friendship , honesty , hard work , comradeship samples shows . Children artistic literature works aesthetic in terms of It is also great for education effect shows . Artistic of works bright images , dear of nature poet landscapes , poems musicality of the language sharpness , expressiveness to the children I like it . Children artistic word they feel the power , so much big didn't happen fairy tales , people singing and poems fast and easily remembering they stay . Artistic to the word love from an early age starting from brought up to go necessary , from kindergarten that 's it for school love with passes and later on Homeland literature loving being remains . People oral creation - fairy tales , riddles , proverbs , songs many of them long in the past and from now on fundamentally difference who does from the event fundamentally difference who does marriage conditions created people creativity from his works only education tasks answer those who give choose is taken . Intelligence or bravery with , patience or work with any _ difficulties overcome brave , conscientious heroes participation which from fairy tales children very they are surprised , like this fairy tales the children positive to the heroes extremely benevolent to be , to evil , to injustice , to anger , to cunning relatively uncompromising to be forced is enough

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uzbek people from fairy tales except many Russian people and in our country another nations fairy tales for children by reading to be given fairy tales including enters _ Russian classic literature from the manifestations A. S. Pushkin , NA Nekrasov, LN Tolstoy, KD Ushinsky and of others works to the children by reading to give to the program included . Uzbek writers , poets children for very a lot great works who created This is G ' . Ghulam , N. Orifjanov , I. Muslim, P. Momin , Sh. Sadulla , Q. Hikmat , Q. Mohammadi and of others works for children by reading to be given of works the richest source is considered

Kindergarten education age to the children dedicated books from the list Russian writers and poets : V. Mayakovsky , A. Kononov , S. Mikhalkov , A. Gaydar, K. Chukovsky and of others translation did works wide place received _ This is the list foreign writers Sh . Perrault , H. K. Andersen and of others fairy tales are also included . To children by reading to be given works range is different genre works : story and stories , prose and poem shaped fairy tales , epics , jokes poems , riddles , parables enters _ Educator each _ young in the group the children very a lot children artistic literature works with by introducing to go it is necessary Educator in children literary the work perception to do skill content finds _ Children's work listening to her content only by mastering it not only _ the author feelings that are being described and he should also feel emotions . of the work content and uniforms analysis of doing some elements are also content will be found . Every child goes to school transition during in the work story done main heroes determine to get them relatively own attitude (whose what for say what you like knowledge of the work form determine should know (poem , story , fairy tale) . In children getting together to hear skills , organization with to questions answer to give and by reading given work based on questions give an illustration attention with out of sight sorry , to the book good in relation to be skills bring up necessary _ Kindergarten in children to the book to give , to know interest , listened work about impressions to share desire and skill educate it is necessary

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Children book to the child understandable was , his mind and to the heart arrived went , that is , of the child writer story doing thing understands and could feel only if it is his own educational role performs _ Educators of children works about knowledge strengthen to go for previous young in groups their which works with acquaintances they know need _ Of this for year At the beginning of previous group program seeing exit and repetition material set take it is necessary Educator calendar-plan make up during near one or two week inside to the children by reading giving his works recommendation from the list set takes _ In

this he is in the children feeling and the behavior is different around interest and relationships content like finding important education common tasks action does _ Children's interested their things _ mutually relationships , games observation good book to choose much help gives _ Each _ the work around known events with tie up and that's it just in time by reading to give to think that it is necessary wrong . Of course , in the book to events depends the subject by reading to give need _ But another at the same time book study transfer it is necessary Educator work after choosing , to the children him how deliver that it is necessary identify take need _ Stranger words a lot that it was for children content understand can't get the work didn't read ok _ In the past historical period with depends has been classic literature of its manifestations in his works , for example , AS Pushkin's fairy tales , folk in fairy tales occurring very a lot stranger the words explanation do you need said question is born These are the words of children work content understand to receive interrupt doesn't give , that's why for them can not be explained . Artistic from literature which uses training great calm conditions requires creation . _ Important , no thing the children from hearing not distracting it is necessary Training fast organize it _ children to literature special healthy , optimistic in character , cheerfulness with transfer need _

RESULTS

Sometimes educator introduction in the word of the work name of the author name , topic known does _ For example , " Today I to you Uzbek people from the fairy tales " Smart girl how by doing hot neck that he cheated by reading I will give Training introduction conversation with start can _ For example , S. Y. Marshak's " On " two months" fairy tale by reading from giving before : Educator : Children , one in how many months are there? do you know Children or educator : Ten two months. Educator : Those months how called ? Children months name they say , educator and necessity _ if their _ the answers fixes it . Educator : The end of a month as soon as the second begins . Not yet when February january without finishing didn't come or May _ April chasing not passed

Months one after another will come and yes when each other with does not meet . But people mountainous Country – Begimia one girl one of time in itself ten two of the month all of them that he saw about story does _ How is this was _ Manna such Then educator from the book read starts _ Fairy tale by reading after all , little girl one of time in itself suddenly ten two month how It is difficult to see at the time months to the little girl how help that he gave and others about conversation spent ok _ Especially moral- aesthetic and to know to the content have has been books by reading in giving thorough preparation is required .

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Moral-aesthetic content books in children moral qualities , behavior positive sides content to find help gives _ Sh. Sadulla's " Whimsical little girl ", LN Tolstoy's " Danak ", V. Oseyeva's " Magnificent the word " works and others so books including enters _ The important thing is the children the book to hear in the process his ideological content understand is to get In this introduction conversation big role plays , teacher such in conversation children attention the most main , important to things attraction is enough For example , to school preparation in the group " Injiq" of Sh. Sadulla girl " poem by reading from giving before educator to the children such question gives : " Guys , do well think and say : how girl about - good girl and how girl about - bad they say ?". Children's answers . Educator : Children , you whose good girl , whose bad girl that it is called right tell me Now I am to you Rosemary said girl about written the poem by reading I will give You guys well done listen and after to me Rosemary good girl to say maybe that it is not you say This poem is " Whimsical is called a girl . The poem a poet Thank you Sadullah wrote _ From this after educator the poem read starts _ Moral-aesthetic content the book from reading before held introduction conversation short to be - from 3-5 minutes not to exceed and of course children experience with connection need (" Whom we are good girl shall we say ?" - this question children to the experience and book to the content focused). Moral-epic content books by reading from being divided and then a

conversation requires transfer . _ Such in conversations very a lot question and explanations not to be because it is necessary children the book reading during heroes behavior _ _ essence deep realize they get Read work about held in conversations the children of heroes behavior right to evaluate to teach and of children hero and his behavior own relationships to say reach it is necessary Sh. Sadullah's his poem from reading after held in conversation to the children capricious girl's behavior to evaluate who help questions to give need _ Educator : Gulbodomni good can it be a girl ? Children's answers . Educator : What? for ? Children's answers . Educator : You such girl with friend to be would you like Why ? Children's answers . Educator : Gulbodomni if you meet to him what said will be were you Children's answers . Educator : Gulbodom to your mother how care to do and help give about what telling will give were you Children's answers . Knowledge giver in character books , for example , labor about books introduction conversation and from reading later the conversation different in content requires to be . Labor about book children for of people professions , cars and work weapons about knowledge source being service is enough Summary by doing in other words , knowledge giver books are different knowledge source only not only _ of people to work respect for nature relatively love and etc qualities bring up tool service as well does _ That's why for book with to work so to the road to put great it is important that it is in children high moral adjectives bring up enable to give need.

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